

CULTURAL AND SOCIAL IDENTITY IN THE WORKS OF CHINUA ACHEBE AND WOLE SOYINKA

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Abstract:

The English is a worldwide language and its literature is so vast as short story writers, poets, novelists, essayists, dramatists and other contributors from various parts of the world have contributed a lot especially during last fifty to sixty years. The American, Indian, French and African writers have expressed the social, cultural and political scenarios of their landscape in their major works especially after getting freedom. The concept of identity is associated with the culture, society, political and geographical scenario of a nation. The classics like Chinua's Things Fall Apart, Soyinka's Death and the King's Horseman and Nagugi's Weep not Child helped a lot in gaining recognition to Modern African Literature all over the world. By winning the Nobel Prize, Soyinka in 1986 added glory to African literature. The language used to write African Literature is European language used in Africa and local African Language. If we compare the African literature to the old oral traditions of literature we find that African literature is very young and new. Africa is very rich in its traditions and cultural heritage. The roots of African Literature lie in performance and the life of common population. It is deeply associated to societal occasions, generation old traditions and rich culture. Chinua Achebe and Wole Soyinka have been considered as the two most influential literary figure in African literature. The present paper is a sincere attempt to analyze cultural and social identity in the works of Chinua Achebe and Wole Soyinka.

Key Words: Indigenous, African Literature, Culture, Tradition, Social Occasions and Identity.

Introduction:

Identity is a multidimensional concept and an individual can have multiple identities in terms of social and cultural. Such individuals have to play the roles of brother, sister, son, daughter, husband, wife, students or as Indian, Chinese, Pakistani or being a part of Europe/ African etc. Moreover the base of identity is historical experiences that are normally based on factors like caste, class, culture, gender, ethnicity or nationality. Though the identity is an individual self but it underlies several social, cultural and political levels and implications. The colonized after facing brutal and bitter experiences with colonizer found themselves insensitive to the portion of colonial means in their identity. It was through education that the colonizers used to control their colonies. Through this means of controlling colonies they controlled the ideas and thoughts of the young generation and imparted colonized ideology or philosophies in their minds. It resulted in loss of their original thoughts, ideas, philosophy and culture. It is because of this during the process of decolonization, post colonial subjects tried to free the minds and control of people and culture along with their land. The era of post colonialism began after gaining the independence and then the local or native people started a search for their original identity and culture. They also analyzed the existing colonial culture. This subject matter formed the base for postcolonial literature.

Post colonial literature expresses the identity connection with the colonizers and also depicts a challenge to build a national identity. This is done by developing and producing a form of literature that argues on social and cultural identity, criticizes the alterations existed during the colonization and by comparing the values, culture and traditions of the two different eras. It also depicts the social, political, cultural changes that exist in postcolonial societies. It also discusses how these changes led to the development of a cross cultural state in society as well as in literature. Marie Napierkowski in Post colonialism: Introduction comments:

"Post-colonialism refers to the representation of culture, race, ethnicity, and identity in the modern world where many countries became independent. While many critics refer to it as the culture and cultural products influenced by imperialism from the moment of colonization until today" (Napierkowski 1998).

In an interview Adam Storlorow stated:

"Postcolonial concerns are about the encounter of cultures. As the editors of The Postcolonial Studies Reader state in the introduction to their collection, post-colonialism addresses all aspects of the colonial process from the beginning of colonial contact. So we could say it begins with the cultural encounter of colonization. Repression and resistance, hybridity and difference all have their start here" (Storlorow, 1997)

Cultural and Social Identity in the Major Works of Chinua Achebe and Wole Soyinka:

The notion of identity is the outcome of colonialism. Postcolonial literature is full of the theme related to identity. This notion of identity is counterfeited by the colonial history and postcolonial dilemma that resulted in the appearance of spatial and cultural essentials. These essentials strongly affected writers of the era and notion of postcolonial identity. After independence, African writers began to express their art; Wole Soyinka declared:

“The artist has always functioned in African society as the record of the mores and experience of his society and as the voice of vision in his own time. It is time for him to respond to this essence of himself.” (Soyinka 23)

His compatriot, Chinua Achebe, revealed two decades later:

“The writer cannot expect to be excused from the task of reeducation and regeneration that must be done. In fact, he should march right in front. [. . .] I for one would not wish to be excused. I would be quite satisfied if my novels (especially the ones I set in the past) did no more than teach my readers that their past – with all its imperfections – was not one long night of savagery from which the first Europeans acting on God’s behalf delivered them..” (Achebe 12)

The present study is concerned with the cultural and social identity in the African nations. Major works of Chinua Achebe and Wole Soyinka have been referred here.

Cultural and Social Identity in the Major Works of Chinua Achebe’s novel Things Fall Apart:

Chinua Achebe is an African writer, poet and novelist. He is also considered as one of the most original literary artists currently writing in English. Achebe was raised by a Christian evangelical in the large village Oxide in Igbo land, Eastern Nigeria. He received his early education in English, but grew up surrounded by the complex fusion of Igbo traditions and colonial legacy. He studied literature and medicine at the University of Ibadan. After graduating, he went to work for the Nigerian broadcasting company in Lagos. *Things Fall Apart*, as his first novel, has been translated into at least forty five languages and focuses on the traditions of Igbo society and the effects of Christian influences on it. He has also been active in Nigerian politics. Achebe portrays the ceremonies of the Igbo tribes as the communal culture. The theorist, Helen Tiffin says:

“*Things Fall Apart* (1950) exposes the festivals and ceremonies as the communal culture, the complexity and communal density of the people’s culture were exposed through festivals, rite and rituals are established... His novel focuses on the Igbo society and his uses of style rely on the Igbo traditions and reputation of rituals and festivals.” (Tiffin 10)

Music and dancing are also a part of Igbo rituals which call for talent, such as that of Oboiza Ezikola. Nwoye was aware of the fact that being masculine was right but he favoured the stories told by his mother. Igbo music is very important and different instruments are used in celebrations. Igbo people keep the music to make gods happy.

Things Fall Apart is a great classic of international literature from Christian missionaries to British colonization. It depicts a traditional community grappling with the arrival of foreign influence. The native people develop a dependence complex resulting in the loss of their innocence and identity. He starts looking upon the coloniser as a master, wittingly or unwittingly, and begins to copy the coloniser’s modes, manners, language, and way of life. Even after getting independence, colonialism is not routed out completely, but neocolonialism establishes its prehistoric characteristics. Cultural Identity Crisis is at the center of the literary art of the novelists Chinua Achebe.

Things Fall Apart presents Okonkwo’s belief in the communal strength of the clan against the cultural dominance of the oppressive colonial power. His trust in his own clan as a community and its culture is shattered into pieces when he returns to Umuofia from exile. He lost his status and identity as a result of colonialism in Nigeria. On his return, he finds himself alien in his clan. He understands that cultural influences change as political power shifts. The new religion, the new administration and western culture have become influential in Umuofia, and native culture starts deteriorating. The encounter between the native culture and newly assimilate one leads to clash of culture in the life of Okonkwo. In this regard the English writers and novelists, David Whittaker and Mplive Msiska suggest:

“*Things Fall Apart* was notable for being the first novel by a West African to portray graphically how colonized subjects perceived the arrival of colonizing European, and one of Achebe’s significant achievement in the novel is the way he succeeds in depicting Umuofia as a vibrant and sophisticated society, with its own complex culture and elaborate moral and ethical codes, while never succumbing a desire to portray it as an idyllic pre-colonial utopia.” (Whittaker and Msiska 20)

The principal character, Okonkwo in *Things Fall Apart* stands for African traditional culture. Okonkwo’s suicide indicates the fall down of the African culture and African identity, which here represents. The sense of alienation forces Okonkwo to commit suicide. The alienation and cultural identity crisis experienced by Okonkwo is unique.

Cultural and Social Identity in the Major Works of Soyinka's Novel the Interpreters:

Akinwande Oluwole Soyinka was the first African writer who won Nobel Prize in literature. He got recognition all over the globe for his adaptable advance to literature. He adopted literature as an agency to promote culture, human rights and social values. As a Nigerian experiencing colonialism and its hardships, he has been standing up for what he believed in by teaching about his culture and by addressing problems through his literary work as well as his political engagement. Falola and Heaton states:

“He has become one of the giants of African theater and literature. A playwright, poet, actor, teacher, social critic, and political activist, Soyinka has written many important works [...] [and] became the first African to win the Nobel Prize for literature.” (Falola and Heaton 30)

Soyinka's debut novel was published in 1965 under the title *The Interpreters*. It was shortly before he was imprisoned. Soyinka has described this novel as “an attempt to capture a particular moment in the life of a generation which was trying to find its feet after independence.” (Soyinka 50) The story is about five friends of whom two have just returned to Nigeria after having studied at universities in Great Britain and America. However since their departure Nigeria has changed and become independent which leaves the group disillusioned and upon their return struggling with their native country, more specifically Lagos. Their respective lives are depicted by a series of flashbacks that interrelate as well as interior monologues unfolding new plots and ideas. This discontinuity, which is a key element of modern literature and resembles Virginia Woolf's complex style of writing, delivers an impression of the characters' common struggle for identity and a place in their home country.

The plot of the story moves around the intellectual class of Nigerian population. Here the interpretation of society by them, discourses by them and their dissatisfaction is depicted. The style of living is also presented through the story. A comparison is made with the society they consider backward and that needs a revolt to change. After independence African leadership took some initiatives and showed a ray of hope to the citizens of Africa. This new power marked the beginning of new era. The black control altered into political traitors. Youth who travelled across to gain knowledge that could help them in assisting the authorities to develop their nation returned and faced a political chaos similar to colonial era.

The Interpreters describes the trivial separation of intellectual class from the society. Soyinka through literature used these intellectuals to show that the individuals are the convincing agent for any kind of transformation in society. The local government took over from the imperial government initiated to improve the materialist nature of its precursor. They had some space for spiritual values as well. So an urgent need was there for an individual to take over the role of evangelism from traditional evangelists as they lack the energy and enthusiasm to carry on.

Conclusion:

It is culture and politics that influenced African literature to high extent. It is because of this only that African literature generally reflects political and cultural aspects. Right from the colonial days, African fiction produces the progression of clashes – political as well as social. These themes are very common among the writers of African literature. The discussed writers in this article also were aware of the political, social, economic and cultural turmoil of the state. Being from a class of intellectual they took a hard stand to various issues and helped to keep alive the issues related to their culture, politics and society.

Through *The Interpreters*, the realities of postcolonial Africa are revealed otherwise that could not be placed in a single narrative. Both the writers were well aware of the diversities that prevailed in their nation rejected stereotyped presentations and rigidly expressed preset and transgressive code of belief. They defined, challenged and described the African culture under the influence of colonizers. They expressed how the old traditions and culture struggled against modern face. They expressed that post colonialism is not only a revolution against old age beliefs but also an evolution of a new world with new values.

Both the writers have same views about social and political conditions of people from African states. Both of them took revolutionary steps on various political and social issues through their writings and helped their nation to keep alive the political and social transformations in their society. Their protagonists show similar struggles, and experiences like those of leaders of struggle movement. They experiences same quandary let loose by the colonial and neo colonial powers in conflict tattered states to which they belong. It can be said that there exists a great thematic unity in the writings of Achebe and Soyinka that can be stated as an expression of their social, political and cultural obligation.

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